

Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines

Updated Landscape Analysis for Priority List of
Adverse events of special interest
Part 2: Chikungunya

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Description of the deliverable	This deliverable provides the methods and results of an updated landscape analysis and priority list of potential adverse events of special interest relevant to Chikungunya vaccine trials
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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ADAMTS13	A disintegrin and metalloproteinase with a thrombospondin type 1 motif, member 13
ADEM	Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis
AEFI	Adverse event following immunization
AESI	Adverse events of special interest
AKI	Acute kidney injury
ANA	Antinuclear antibody
ARDS	Acute respiratory distress syndrome
ALT	Alanine aminotransferase
AST	Aspartate aminotransferase
BC	Brighton Collaboration
BCG	Bacillus Calmette-Guerin
BUN	Blood urea nitrogen
CD	Case definition
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CEP	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness and Innovation
CHIK	Chikungunya
CHIKV	Chikungunya virus
CIOMS	Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
CMV	Cytomegalovirus
CPK	Creatine phosphokinase
COPD	Chronic obstructive lung disease
CT	Computed tomography
DENV	Dengue virus
DIC	Disseminated intravascular coagulation
EBV	Epstein Barr Virus
GBS	Guillain barré syndrome
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
HUS	Hemolytic uremic syndrome
ICU	Intensive care unit
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
LFT	Liver function test
KDIGO	Kidney Disease – Improving Global Outcome
mL	Milliliter
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
MVA	Modified vaccinia
Nkat/L	Nanokatal / Liter
PRISMA	Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses

RT-PCR	Reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction
r-VSV	Recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus
SD	Standard deviation
SIADH	Syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone secretion
SNHL	Sensorineural hearing loss
SOFA	Sequential organ failure assessment
SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines
SpO2	Hemoglobin oxygen saturation (expressed as a percentage - %)
sTM	Soluble thrombomodulin
TB	Tuberculosis
TBD	To be decided
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
TTP	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura
U/L	Units per liter
VAED	Vaccine-associated enhanced disease
VSV	Vesiculostomatitis virus
WBC	White blood cell
ZIKAV	Zika virus

1. Background

CEPI contracted the Brighton Collaboration, through the Task Force for Global Health, to harmonize safety assessment across CEPI funded vaccine development. Since inception, a key activity of SPEAC (Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines) has been to establish lists of adverse events of special interest (AESI) that have potential to occur during CEPI-funded clinical trials.

Adverse events of special interest

An adverse event following immunization (AEFI) is defined as ‘any untoward medical occurrence which follows immunization, and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with the usage of the vaccine. The adverse event may be any unfavorable or unintended sign, abnormal laboratory finding, symptom or disease.’¹

The source definition of ‘Adverse Event of Special Interest’ (AESI) as defined in CIOMS VII² is:

“An adverse event of special interest (serious or non-serious) is one of scientific and medical concern specific to the sponsor’s product or program, for which ongoing monitoring and rapid communication by the investigator to the sponsor could be appropriate. Such an event might require further investigation in order to characterize and understand it. Depending on the nature of the event, rapid communication by the trial sponsor to other parties (e.g., regulators) might also be warranted.”

AESIs can be specified in the Program Safety Analysis plan early in product development for safety planning, data collection, analysis and reporting on AESI data, and eventually form the base of AESI analysis in the Reporting and Analysis Plan.

Vaccine safety is evaluated ~~needs to be conducted~~ across the entire life cycle of vaccine development, approval and use. It is essential that the approach be harmonized and standardized so that data are comparable across different trials and populations. Thus, while several if not most of the AESIs identified as relevant to CEPI vaccine programs are likely to be rare events and may never occur in the context of a given trial, preparations must be made to maximize the utility of vaccine safety data so appropriate risk-benefit decisions can be made.

SPEAC has chosen to identify possible AESIs for specific diseases using 4 main criteria as outlined below. The AESIs that were included on the 2020 Chikungunya list are shown for each criterion:

1. AESIs that have been previously identified with immunization in general:
 - a. Anaphylaxis, thrombocytopenia, generalized convulsive seizure
2. AESIs associated with specific vaccines:
 - a. Live attenuated vaccines: aseptic meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis
 - b. Vesiculostomatitis virus vaccine: acute aseptic arthritis
 - c. mRNA and modified vaccinia virus vaccines: myocarditis
 - d. Adenovirus vector vaccines: TTS / VITT
 - e. Pandemic and some seasonal influenza vaccines: Guillain Barré Syndrome
3. AESIs that may occur during the clinical course or as a complication of the chosen target diseases due to viral replication or the host immune response:
 - a. Cardiovascular: myocarditis, pericarditis
 - b. Dermatologic: rash, alopecia
 - c. Eye: Uveitis, retinitis, optic neuritis
 - d. Hematologic: thrombocytopenia, thrombosis and thromboembolism, hemorrhagic disease
 - e. Hepatic: hepatic dysfunction / failure
 - f. Musculoskeletal: acute and chronic inflammatory rheumatism

- g. Neurologic: aseptic meningitis, encephalitis / myelitis, seizure, ADEM, GBS, Bell's palsy
- h. Renal: acute kidney injury, acute renal failure
- i. Pregnancy outcomes: spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, neonatal sepsis/encephalopathy via peripartum infection; neurodevelopmental delay following neonatal infection

The [initial landscape analysis for Chikungunya AESI](#) was completed in March 2020 and was based on a targeted literature review of key review articles.

2. Objective of this deliverable

The primary objective is to update the 2020 landscape analysis and AESI list for potential safety issues relevant to development of Chikungunya vaccines based on a systematic literature review.

3. Methods

A scoping review was conducted according to PRISMA Guidelines Extension for scoping reviews³. The initial part of the review was done by a subcontractor as outlined in their report in Appendix 1. This included: developing the primary search strategies for Medline (OVID), Embase (OVID) and CINAHL (EBSCO Host); running the search (on Feb 14, 2024); screening out duplicates; and excluding noncontributory articles based on title and abstract.

The full text of all articles included after the preliminary screening were reviewed by the author of the original Chikungunya landscape analysis (B. Law). Each included article was reviewed in detail and descriptive notes made on the key findings. A standard data extraction form was not used.

Exclusion criteria at this stage included the following:

- Articles that focused on specific AESI already included in the 2020 AESI list (e.g. article focused on GBS following Chikungunya infection).
- Articles containing only: animal model data; Chikungunya viral regional genotype data; regional outbreaks or seroprevalence data with no detailed descriptions of clinical presentation or complications; theoretical discussions of pathogenesis.
- Articles that were cited in the 2020 landscape analysis.
- Articles that had a special population focus (pregnancy, pediatric, immunocompromised host).

All review (systematic and non-systematic) articles were reviewed specifically to identify citations that might provide evidence relevant to the AESI landscape analysis update. Clinical descriptive articles that focused broadly on specific body system complications were reviewed to ensure that any new potential AESI were recognized. Case reports of entities not on the 2020 AESI list were included and the citations searched to identify any additional articles relevant to the given entity.

The above search was focused on Chikungunya clinical disease as a source for potential AESIs.

4. Results

Literature Search

Appendix 1, Figure 1 shows the Prisma diagram for the initial part of the literature review done by the subcontractor.

Briefly 1325 articles were retrieved based on the search strategies for PubMed, Embase and CINAHL. There were 115 duplicates identified leaving 1210 articles for Title and Abstract screening after which 873 articles were excluded as irrelevant to the literature search objective. Among the 336 articles all had full text review except 3 which could not be retrieved. Of 333 reviewed, 167 were excluded because of: no outcome of interest (40); previously identified AESI (115); outcome reported for co-infection only (1); not primary data (1); unavailable in English (10).

This left 166 articles for full text review by the original author of the first Chikungunya landscape analysis (BL). 1 article was excluded because it was cited in the 2020 Chikungunya landscape analysis.⁴ All remaining 165 articles were read and citations manually searched, resulting in an additional 64 articles selected for full text review. After reviewing the full text articles, 27 contributed to the Chikungunya landscape analysis update,⁵⁻³¹ whereas 167 provided no new potential AESIs³²⁻¹⁹⁸ and 35 focused only on special populations¹⁹⁹⁻²³³ (as summarized in Table 2) which are beyond the scope of this update. All articles addressing Chikungunya in special populations were forwarded to SPEAC colleagues in Work Package 5.

Table 1. Classification of articles included in the Chikungunya landscape analysis by study focus, source, and whether it contributed to the AESI list update.

Contributory to AESI update	YES		NO	
	Literature Search	Citation Hand Search	Literature Search	Citation Hand Search
Citation Source				
Focus of Study				
1. Reviews	0	0	10 ³²⁻⁴¹	3 ⁴²⁻⁴⁴
2. Animal Study	0	0	1 ⁴⁵	0
3. CHIK case definition	0	0	1 ⁴⁶	1 ⁴⁷
4. CHIK co-infection	0	0	4 ⁴⁸⁻⁵¹	1 ⁵²
5. CHIK genotype	0	0	1 ⁵³	0
6. Epidemiology-non-clinical	0	0	1 ⁵⁴	1 ⁵⁵
7. Fatal outcome	2 ^{5,6}	1 ⁷	2 ^{56,57}	8 ⁵⁸⁻⁶⁵
8. Pathogenesis	0	0	6 ⁶⁶⁻⁷¹	3 ⁷²⁻⁷⁴
9. Regional outbreak descriptions	0	0	33 ^{75-97,99-108}	7 ^{98,109-114}
10. Seroprevalence	0	0	3 ¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁷	0
11. Chikungunya vaccine trials	0	0	5 ¹¹⁸⁻¹²²	1 ¹²³
12. Clinical case reports/series of travel-acquired chikungunya	0	0	4 ¹²⁴⁻¹²⁷	0
13. Clinical Descriptive studies	1 ⁸	5 ⁹⁻¹³	2 ^{128,129}	5 ¹³⁰⁻¹³⁴
14. Autoimmune disease	0	0	1 ¹³⁵	0
15. Cardiac disease	0	0	3 ¹³⁶⁻¹³⁸	0
16. Ear	2 ^{14,15}	1 ¹⁶	0	2 ^{139,140}
17. Eye	2 ^{17,18}	0	12 ¹⁴¹⁻¹⁵²	1 ¹⁵³

18. Hematologic	1 ¹⁹	0	0	0
19. Liver	0	0	1 ¹⁵⁴	0
20. Musculoskeletal	3 ²⁰⁻²²	1 ²³	12 ¹⁵⁵⁻¹⁶⁶	8 ¹⁶⁷⁻¹⁷⁴
21. Neurologic	1 ²⁴	0	9 ¹⁷⁵⁻¹⁸³	2 ^{184, 185}
22. Renal	1 ²⁵	0	3 ¹⁸⁶⁻¹⁸⁸	0
23. Respiratory	2 ^{26, 27}	0	0	1 ¹⁸⁹
24. Skin/Mucosa	2 ^{28, 29}	2 ^{30, 31}	3 ¹⁹⁰⁻¹⁹²	6 ¹⁹³⁻¹⁹⁸
SUBTOTAL	17	10	117	50

Table 2. Articles with focus on special population only

Special Population Relevance (not reviewed)	Literature Search	Citation Search
Pregnancy	11 ¹⁹⁹⁻²⁰⁹	1 ²¹⁰
Foetus	2 ^{211, 212}	0
Newborn / Infants / Children	13 ²¹³⁻²²⁵	3 ²²⁶⁻²²⁸
Immunocompromised Host	4 ²²⁹⁻²³²	1 ²³³
SUBTOTAL	30	5

Each of the 27 articles included for this landscape analysis update are summarized below:

Fatal Outcome^{5, 6, 7}

De Lima et al⁵ provided details of 68 fatalities with confirmed CHIKV infection during a 2017 outbreak in Brazil. Coinfection with other arboviruses was found in 18 (15 DENV, 2 Zika, 1 DENV + Zika) but the remaining 50 had CHIKV alone. Information on comorbidities was available for 44 cases and of these 20 had none (45.5%) and 24 had 1 to 3 comorbidities, primarily hypertension or diabetes. Those with no comorbidities were younger with a mean age (range) of 37.4 years (3 days to 79 years) relative to those with ≥ 1 comorbidity (mean 60 years; range 31-85 years). Among 42 autopsied cases, cardiac and/or respiratory failure was the cause of death in 32 (76.2%). Multiple organ dysfunction was common with hepatitis in 58.5%, pneumonitis in 52.4%, myocarditis in 36.6% and encephalitis in 21.4%. Several different findings were noted in the lungs including 90% with edema and/or alveolar proteinosis, 60% emphysema, 58% hemorrhage, 55% atelectasis, 58% pneumonitis, 25% bronchopneumonia or bronchitis, 12% hyaline membranes, 5-6% necrosis or pleuritis and <5% with bronchiolitis. Unfortunately, there was no presentation of data for those without comorbidities who were infected with CHIKV alone, making it difficult to ascribe findings to CHIKV.

Sharp et al⁶ utilized the Enhanced Fatal Acute Febrile Illness Surveillance System set up by the US CDC and Puerto Rico Department of Health to identify fatal cases of CHIK infection. They defined sepsis as having the following within 1 week prior to death: fever $\geq 38.0^\circ\text{C}$; leukocytosis (WBC $>12,000$ cells/ mL^3) or leukopenia (WBC $<4,000$ cells/ mL^3); and acute organ dysfunction as indicated by ≥ 1 of: mechanical ventilation; serum bilirubin ≥ 2.0 mg/dL; serum creatinine ≥ 2.0 mg/dL; thrombocytopenia ($<100,000$ platelets/ mL^3). Septic shock was defined as sepsis (using definition above) and vasopressor therapy. CHIKV infection was confirmed by RT-PCR in blood or postmortem tissue in 30 (58%) of 58 fatal cases. Individual medical information was available for 27 confirmed CHIK case-patients. All but 2 (7%) had comorbidities with hypertension, diabetes and obesity being the most common. Among those with no comorbidity was a 9-year-old girl who died at home within 2 days of onset, presumably of septic shock. The median time from illness onset to death was 4 days (range 1-29 days). Most cases presented with fever, arthralgia, myalgia, lethargy and rash. CHIKV antigen was detected in at least 1 tissue

specimen from 11 fatal cases. Of these 1 met the case definition for sepsis and 2 met the case definitions for both sepsis and septic shock .

Torres et al⁷ reported 3 fatal Chikungunya cases among Venezuelan adults with confirmed CHIK infection and other infections ruled out by extensive testing. A 75-year-old man with no known comorbidities was admitted to hospital 3 days after symptoms onset with severe sepsis and multiple organ failure and died within 72 hours of admission. A 53-year-old female with a history of iron deficiency anemia but no other noted comorbidities was admitted after 3 days of a typical CHIK febrile illness. Within 72 hours of admission, she died with multiorgan failure, DIC, hemodynamic instability and necrosis of the skin overlying her nose. A 65-year-old man with known hypertension was admitted after 4 days of a typical CHIK febrile illness and died within 24 hours with multiorgan failure, shock, respiratory failure and generalized ecchymoses.

Clinical Descriptive Studies ⁸⁻¹³

Four studies focused on patients with severe chikungunya infection requiring intensive care. Key details of these studies are summarized in Table 3.

Possibly the first report of serious CHIKV acute infection in adults came from the Reunion Island outbreak of 2005/2006. Lemant et⁹ did a case series study in the ICU of the South Reunion Hospital which was noted to have standards of care like hospitals in France. CHIKV infection was confirmed in 33 of 48 suspect cases admitted to ICU. The mean age was 60 (SD 15; median 62; range 23-86) years. At least one comorbidity was identified in 73% of cases, including diabetes, cardiac failure, renal failure and COPD. There were 7 confirmed co-infections that could have accounted for the severe disease (2 *S. pneumoniae*, 2 *E. coli*, 1 *H. influenzae*, 1 *Klebsiella* sp., 1 *C. albicans*). Although most cases were older with comorbid disease(s), there were four individuals under 50 years of age (26, 40, 41, 45,) with no comorbidity who had a severe course of infection. There were only 2 cases noted by the authors, in a table listing case by case diagnoses, to have “septic shock (*Pneumoniae*)”. The meaning of “*Pneumoniae*” was not provided and thus it was difficult to be sure the shock was attributable to CHIKV.

Dileep et al⁸ did a 3-year prospective study of CHIKV infected patients admitted to a tertiary care center ICU in West India between September 1, 2016, and August 31, 2019. Cases had to have fever, be aged >16 years and have CHIKV infection confirmed by RT-PCR or IgM. Patients with chronic arthritis, skin disease or pregnancy were excluded. Among 470 screened patients 52 were enrolled in the study. There were 7 with DENV co-infection. Most had comorbidities: 90% hypertension; 47% diabetes; 13% chronic kidney disease. Only 3.8% had no comorbidity (2 cases). A notable finding, not found in the first landscape analysis, was rhabdomyolysis, present in 78% (n=36) of cases with the highest CPK level of 7988 U/L. Otherwise cases had expected clinical manifestations of encephalitis, thrombocytopenia and skin rash.

Crosby et al¹⁰ studied patients admitted to ICU in university hospitals of Guadeloupe and Martinique from January to November 2014. Patients were included if they had confirmed CHIKV infection (RT-PCR or IgM serology). The median age was 63 years (Interquartile range 52-70). Organ failure was assessed within 48 hours of admission and defined as having a SOFA score of 3 or 4. Of 6 patients with septic shock (n=3) or severe sepsis (n=3) the only infectious agent identified was CHIKV. The proportion with organ failure apparent during the first 48 hours after admission (based on a SOFA score of 3 or 4) was: 45% hemodynamic; 41% renal; 28% neurologic; 26% respiratory; 26% hepatic; and 20% hematologic. The authors noted that the complication of CHIKV-related severe sepsis or septic shock had not been observed in previous outbreak reports.

Koeltz et al¹¹ described the characteristics and course of 64 patients admitted to ICU in Tahiti during the 2014-2015 CHIK outbreak. There were only 3 co-infections confirmed but 76% had comorbidities. They identified 21

(33%) cases of severe sepsis based on a standard definition of septic shock and organ system failures (SOFA score). Based on RT-PCR they noted a high viral load in serum with median of 7.52 log₁₀ copies/mL (Interquartile range: 3.47-9.39). The proportion with organ failure at admission (based on SOFA score of ≥ 3 for each system) were: 63% hemodynamic; 52% respiratory; 47% renal; 31% neurologic; 25% hepatic and 14% hematologic.

Table 3. Descriptive studies of patients admitted to ICU with confirmed CHIKV infection

Author / Location	Study Period	Confirmed CHIKV Infection	Age in years	Comorbidities	Co-infection	Events not on 2020 AESI list
Dileep ⁸ West India	1Sep16 to 31Aug16	52	Range 24-89	96.2%	7 (13.5%) Dengue	36 (78%) rhabdomyolyses Highest CPK of 7988 U/L
Lemant ⁹ Reunion Island	Aug05 to May06	33	Mean 60.9 SD 15.7	73%	8 (24.2%) bacterial pathogens	22 (85%) rhabdomyolysis 10 (38%) septic shock
Crosby ¹⁰ Guadeloupe & Martinique	Jan to Nov 14	65	Median 60 IQR 52-65	83%	None specified	37 (57%) respiratory failure 30 (46%) shock 6 (9.2%) septic shock
Koeltz ¹¹ Tahiti	May14 to March15	64	Median 62 IQR 49-71	76%	2 leptospirosis 1 Dengue	40 (62%) shock 33 (51%) respiratory failure 21 (33%) severe sepsis

Rolle et al¹² collected case data using a standardized form for all nonpregnant adult patients admitted to the University Hospital of Pointe-a-Pitre, Guadeloupe with a positive CHIKV RT-PCR test during the 2014 CHIK outbreak. Of 110 CHIK infected adults 42 (38%) had a severe form of the disease defined as ≥ 1 organ system failure or admission to ICU. The proportion of severe cases that met the definition of severe sepsis was 60% (n=25) and the proportion with failure of specific organs was: 52% cardio-circulatory; 50% respiratory; 36% renal; 21% liver and 14% neurologic. Several had comorbidities but it was not possible to determine the proportion with ≥ 1 comorbidity. The most common were diabetes mellitus in 38% and chronic heart disease in 28%. Among the 25 classified as having severe sepsis CHIKV was the only pathogen identified based on blood and urine cultures.

Economopoulou et al¹³ described a large series of atypical CHIKV infections during the Reunion Island 2005/2006 CHIK outbreak. Atypical disease was defined as a case with ≥ 1 symptom aside from fever or arthralgia plus lab evidence of acute or recent CHIKV infection. A total of 610 atypical cases were identified in adults of whom 89% had comorbidities. Unusual complications, not previously on the AESI list included 12 cases of pancreatitis, 6 cases of SIADH and 6 cases of hypoadrenalism. There was no discussion of the individual cases, and it wasn't possible to determine whether the unusual presentations had underlying disease that might explain or predispose to the observed problems.

Hearing Loss¹⁴⁻¹⁶

There were no otologic AESIs including SNHL identified in the first chikungunya landscape analysis.

Bhavana et al¹⁴ published a case report of SNHL in a 15-year-old girl that onset 1 week after a typical chikungunya infection with fever, arthralgia and rash that was confirmed by IgM ELISA. Audiometry showed a profound SNHL on the left that didn't improve by one month after onset. No specific details of the audiometry were presented.

Venancio et al¹⁵ did a scoping review of hearing changes in adults with CHIKV, DENV or ZIKAV infection. Three articles focused on CHIKV in 239 individuals. A slight degree of hearing loss was a symptom among 5.85% but sensorineural hearing loss was only reported in one individual in a single study¹⁶, which had not been identified in the literature search but was retrieved for full text review. The main objective of the study by Dutta et al¹⁶ was to determine the prevalence of CHIKV activity in Assam, Northeast India. Of 280 sera samples collected from patients with fever, headache and joint pain only 10 were confirmed to have CHIKV by IgM ELISA. They had no evidence of other viruses. One of the 10 was noted to have bilateral mild to severe SNHL based on audiometry but no results were presented.

Inflammatory Eye Disease ^{17, 18}

Inflammatory eye disease, including uveitis, retinitis and optic neuritis were already on the AESI list produced during the first chikungunya landscape analysis. Two articles found in the literature review were included because they focused on optic neuritis, and it was hoped to get a better understanding of the nature of the eye inflammation associated with chikungunya as well as the diagnostic approach in LMICs since both studies were done in India.

Mittal et al¹⁷ presented an observational case series of 14 patients with proven CHIKV infection by IgM ELISA during the 2006 CHIK outbreak in South India. All had clinical features of optic neuritis. All had a complete ophthalmic exam including determination of intraocular pressure by applanation tonometry, indirect ophthalmoscopy of the dilated fundus, slitlamp biomicroscopy of the anterior and posterior segments, color vision and visual field examination. In addition, at the first visit visual evoked potentials and neuroimaging tests were done. Tests were done to rule out dengue, typhoid fever, malaria, TB and syphilis. Acute optic neuritis was confirmed in all 14 cases with the following specific diagnoses: papillitis alone in 5, papillitis with cranial nerve VII palsy in 1, neuroretinitis in 3, retrobulbar neuritis in 3 and optic tract demyelination in 2. In 5 cases the ocular symptoms were concurrent with the acute disease suggesting possible direct viral effect. In the other 9 the optic neuritis developed after the acute infection suggesting an immunopathogenic process.

Rose et al¹⁸ conducted an observational study of acute optic neuritis following chikungunya infection during an outbreak in Kerala in southern rural india from July 12 to August 21, 2007. Infection was confirmed in 10 patients who were seen in the Department of Ophthalmology at Kottayam Medical College. All cases were positive for CHIKV IgM and negative tests for ANA, blood culture, Widal test, Mantoux test, IgM leptospiral antibody, IgM dengue antibody, syphilis and retroviral antibody tests. All had complete ophthalmic examinations including visual acuity, color vision, visual fields, intraocular pressure by tonometry, indirect ophthalmoscopy, slit lamp exam and visual evoked potentials. Optic neuritis was confirmed in all 10, bilateral in 3 and unilateral in 7. Specific diagnoses were unilateral papillitis in 4, bilateral papillitis in 3, retrobulbar neuritis in 1, perineuritis in 1 and neuroretinitis in 1. Unlike the series by Mittal, all 10 cases of optic neuritis followed 1 to 6 weeks after the acute CHIK infection suggesting an immune-mediated pathogenesis.

Hematologic Disorders ¹⁹

The first CHIK landscape analysis identified thrombosis/thromboembolism and hemorrhagic disease as AESI. The only new entity identified in this update was TTP (thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura) based on a single case report by Kumar et al.¹⁹ This concerned a 24-year-old female from New Delhi with no comorbidities who had confirmed CHIK while negative for other infectious etiologies (dengue, malaria, leptospirosis, scrub typhus, HIV, hepatitis B and C). She developed a purpuric rash and decreased urine output 4 days after the typical onset of acute fever and polyarthralgia. HUS (hemolytic uremic syndrome) was considered but ruled out when the

decreased urine output normalized after 2 days. Lab tests showed thrombocytopenia, anemia, schistocytes and elevated LDH and indirect bilirubin. Skin biopsy showed microvascular occlusion with no vasculitis. Definitive testing for TTP (ADAMTS13) was unavailable but a PLASMIC score of 7 was predictive of ADAMTS13 activity of <10% normal. An extensive workup for other causes of a hypercoagulable state revealed no alternative diagnosis. A second case report of TTP following CHIKV infection was found in a hand search of citations but could not be retrieved. (Epelboin L, Bidaud B, Mosnier E et al. Fatal case of chikungunya and concomitant thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura in French Guiana during air flight medical evacuation. *J Travel Med* 2017; 24(5): <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/tax028> . PMID 28499011).

Musculoskeletal Disorders ²⁰⁻²³

Acute and chronic inflammatory rheumatism were featured on the first CHIK AESI list and included multiple entities (synovitis, tendinitis, enthesitis, bursitis and combinations of the aforementioned). Two new musculoskeletal entities were found in the updated review: rhabdomyolysis^{20, 21} and inflammatory myositis.²²

Elfert et al²⁰ presented a case report of CHIK-related rhabdomyolysis in a 34-year-old, previously healthy male who had recently travelled to India and Qatar. CHIKV infection was confirmed by positive IgM test and tests for other infections (dengue, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, HIV, adenovirus, CMV, EBV) were negative. CPK was >2000 U/L (normal range of 39-308 U/L) and other lab parameters were unremarkable. Symptoms of rhabdomyolysis included dark urine and muscle tenderness in shoulder and thigh muscles. No muscle biopsy was done but the authors cited a study by Ozden et al²³ of two CHIKV infected patients where viral antigens were found inside skeletal muscle progenitor ‘satellite cells’ but not in muscle fibres. The same authors demonstrated the ability of CHIKV to replicate in human satellite cells. The involvement of satellite cells was linked to possible chronic myalgia, but it was not clear how it would lead to rhabdomyolysis.

Kruys et al²¹ presented a case of CHIK-associated rhabdomyolysis in an 11-year-old Indo-Surinamese boy. The boy presented with fever and muscular pain in arms and legs for four days and two days of passing dark urine. Serum CPK was 32,235 U/L (normal lab range 38-174 U/L). He responded to aggressive isotonic saline fluid therapy with normalization of the CK levels over a week in hospital and he was discharged home having developed no other complications. CHIKV infection was confirmed by RT-PCR.

Dev et al²² presented a case report of CHIK-induced inflammatory myositis in 35-year-old woman from New Delhi who presented with a five-day history of fever, weakness and pain in all four limbs. CHIKV infection was confirmed by IgM ELISA. CPK was 214,300 nkat/L. No lab normal range was provided. Investigations for connective tissue disorders, vasculitis, thyroid and parathyroid disorders, vitamin D deficiency, leptospirosis, Lyme disease, rickettsia, malaria, dengue and HIV were all negative as were repeated bacterial and fungal blood and urine cultures. Muscle biopsy was consistent with inflammatory myositis. Nothing was stated regarding efforts to recover or identify CHIKV in the muscle biopsy tissue.

Neurologic Disorders ²⁴

Silva et al reported a single case of peripheral polyneuropathy in a 66-year-old Brazilian female. Nerve conduction studies showed a sensory-motor axonal pattern of peripheral neuropathy. This could have been a rare GBS variant but there was no discussion of this possibility and insufficient information presented to rule GBS in or out.

Renal Disorders ²⁵

AKI (acute kidney injury) manifesting as renal dysfunction and acute renal failure were both included on the first CHIK AESI list. Costa et al²⁴ conducted a scoping review to assess the relationship between CHIKV and the kidneys focusing on the current state of knowledge regarding an association of AKI with CHIK including the incidence in acute infection, presenting features, risk factors and impact of pre-existing kidney injury on disease evolution. They included English articles involving adults with CHIKV infection. A total of 54 articles were included in the final review. It is beyond the scope of this update to describe all that was found in the review. The authors concluded that AKI is associated with atypical and severe CHIKV infection particularly in cases with septic shock. They found no evidence of a direct relationship between viremia alone and the risk of AKI. While some studies have shown CHIKV antigen in renal tissue there was no apparent cytopathic effect histopathologically. AKI during the course of CHIKV infection was noted to be associated with poorer outcomes. Despite the abundance of articles reviewed there was no definitive understanding of mechanisms for AKI during CHIKV infection and most likely it is a multifactorial process. They noted that possible mechanisms included immune complex formation, direct viral damage to kidney tissue, triggering of underlying conditions such as glomerulopathies or atypical HUS, complications from infection or its treatment, hemodynamic changes and rhabdomyolysis.

Respiratory Disorders ^{26, 27}

Two case reports noted respiratory involvement in CHIK. Ahmed et al²⁶ reported a case of diffuse alveolar hemorrhage in a 28-year-old previously healthy Turkish man. He presented to the emergency department with 3 days of fever and shortness of breath and an episode of hemoptysis the day of admission. An initial diagnosis of pneumonia was made based on chest radiographs, but high-resolution CT of the chest was more consistent with pulmonary alveolar hemorrhages with possible secondary pulmonary infection. CHIK was suspected because several family members were ill with fever and arthralgias. Subsequently it was confirmed by a positive IgM test. This was the first known report of alveolar hemorrhage complicating CHIK. The authors postulated that it may have been due to a direct effect of the virus or an idiopathic reaction to viral infection.

Singh²⁷ reported a case of ARDS (acute respiratory distress syndrome) in a previously healthy 24-year-old male from New Delhi. CHIKV was confirmed with a positive ELISA IgM and other infections, including dengue, leptospirosis, malaria, typhoid fever, meningococemia, scrub typhus, rickettsia and other viral, bacterial or parasitic causes were ruled out.

Skin and Mucosal Disorders ²⁸⁻³¹

Vinay et al²⁸ published an overview of the mucocutaneous manifestations seen in CHIK. As dermatologists they drew from their own observations of patients seen in their practice during the 2016 and 2022 outbreaks in Chandigarh, India. They supplemented this with a nonsystematic literature review up to December 2022. They categorized presenting signs and symptoms as early onset (within 1 month of fever onset) and late onset (>1 month after fever onset). Early onset presentations included maculopapular rashes, vesiculobullous eruptions, lesions resembling Stevens Johnson syndrome or toxic epidermal necrolysis, scrotal dermatitis, urogenital ulcers and exacerbation of prior dermatologic diseases like psoriasis. Late onset presentations included hyperpigmentation, lichenoid eruptions, alopecia and exacerbation of acne. They presented a lot of detail and pictures of hyperpigmentation and a table of the many differential diagnoses that could also cause hyperpigmentation. It is beyond the scope of this analysis to go into detail of their presentation, but it is an excellent source of dermatological presentations that may occur in CHIKV infection as well as other diseases.

The review by Vinay et al cited 7 studies of which only one mentioned alopecia. Kaleem et al²⁸ conducted an observational cross-sectional study in the Dermatology department of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre in

Karachi from May 15, 2018, to Jan 15, 2019. They included 67 suspected cases of CHIK fever (based on sudden onset of fever with multiple other symptoms including arthralgia, backache, headache, photophobia and rash presenting during a local CHIK outbreak) of whom 40 were confirmed by serology. Alopecia occurred in 25% of the 40 confirmed cases and 15% of the serologically negative patients. Alopecia was a late manifestation with most reported 2 to 3 months after the acute febrile illness. They noted that other causes of alopecia were excluded including diffuse alopecia, telogen effluvium, tinea capitis, Vitamin D3 deficiency, anemia, thyroid disorders, other inflammatory conditions or drug exposure such as oral contraceptive pills, anticoagulants or anticonvulsants.

Two other of the 7 studies cited by Vinay were obtained and reviewed because they focused on or included children. Seetharam et al³⁰ described cutaneous manifestations of CHIK among 52 children attending their outpatient dermatology clinic in Katuri Medical College in Guntur, India in 2009 and 2010. All cases were confirmed by positive IgM antibody tests. There was minimal demographic data presented but it was noted that 22 cases were infants with the youngest being 22 days old. The range of manifestations was similar to that summarized by Vinay et al, with most cases having diffuse or macular pigmentation (52%), maculopapular (27%) or vesiculobullous (30.7%) rashes. There were 5 cases who had peeling of skin that resembled staphylococcal scalded skin syndrome but none of the children were irritable nor were lesions tender.

Riyaz et al³¹ described 162 patients attending their outpatient dermatology clinic at Calicut Medical College in India. All had serologically confirmed CHIKV infection. As found by others, erythematous macules (34%), maculopapular rash (20%) or vesicles and bullae (13%) were the most common presentations. One unique feature in seven cases was localized erythema and swelling of the pinnae which was similar to Milian's sign seen in erysipelas. Another four cases had erythema and edema of pre-existing scars (post traumatic or related to prior BCG vaccination). Pigmentary changes were also common (seen in 38%) with the majority (52 out of 62 cases) involving the nose.

Excluded Studies³²⁻¹⁹⁸

Most studies that had full text review had nothing unusual to inform updates to the CHIK AESI list. Reports of regional CHIK outbreaks⁷⁵⁻¹¹⁴ were thoroughly reviewed but no evidence was found to suggest the clinical course and complications of CHIKV infection differed over time and place. Six excluded studies focused on CHIK vaccines.¹¹⁹⁻¹²⁴ Four were CHIK vaccine trials.^{119-121, 124} Review of a recently available ongoing living systematic review of CHIK vaccines that is being conducted by WP5, showed there are 18 human clinical trials to date including the four found in this search. The living systematic review will be the definitive source of vaccine safety data that may inform the CHIK AESI list. Given the timing of the release (Jan 28, 2025) and the need to complete the landscape update based on CHIK disease nothing further on vaccines will be presented or considered here.

5. Discussion & Recommendations

Based on the evidence presented above, the recommended addition to the CHIK AESI list is severe CHIKV infection which consists of shock-like presentation with multiple organ failure. The published Brighton Case Definition for Viscerotropic Disease²³⁵ was designed to be applicable to vaccines other than Yellow Fever. The definition provides major and minor criteria for organ failure related to cardiovascular (hypotension), respiratory (respiratory failure), renal (acute kidney injury), hepatic (acute hepatic dysfunction), hematologic (hemorrhagic disease or platelet disorder) or musculoskeletal (rhabdomyolysis) involvement.

Live-attenuated CHIK vaccines could potentially cause severe infection if given to immunocompromised hosts. Another possible mechanism would be as a vaccine-associated-enhanced disease (VAED). There is a Brighton CD for VAED²³⁶ but it is not intended for application to single cases. The viscerotropic disease CD can be applied to individual cases and provide a degree of diagnostic certainty regarding multiple organ failure should it occur.

Single organ cutaneous vasculitis has also been added based on what has been observed with the r-VSV platform.

Rhabdomyolysis, TTP, SNHL, pancreatitis, SIADH, hypoadrenalism, diffuse alveolar hemorrhage and ARDS were noted in some of the studies reviewed above but are not added to the AESI list at this time because they were isolated case reports or small series from single locations and the evidence for an association with CHIK was not compelling.

The updated list is shown in Table 4 below along with an indication of whether there is a Brighton CD or an accompanying Companion Guide for each listed AESI.

Table 4. Revised CHIK AESI List (Additions to the original 2020 list are highlighted in yellow)

Body System	AESI	CHIK disease	Vaccine	Brighton CD	Companion Guide
Cardiac	Myocarditis / Pericarditis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	mRNA, MVA platforms	YES	YES
Eye	Uveitis/Retinitis/Optic neuritis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		2025	2025
Hematologic	Hemorrhagic disease	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NO ¹	NO
	Thrombocytopenia	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All vaccines	YES	YES
	Thrombosis and Thromboembolism	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		YES	YES
	TTS/VITT		Adeno vectors	YES	YES
Hepatic	Hepatic dysfunction / failure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NO ^{1,2}	NO
Multisystem	Anaphylaxis		All vaccines	YES	YES
	Severe CHIKV infection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		YES ³	NO
Musculo-skeletal	Acute aseptic arthritis		r-VSV platform	YES	YES
	Acute/chronic Inflammatory Rheumatism	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		2025	2025
Neurologic	Generalized convulsion	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All vaccines	YES	YES
	Aseptic meningitis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Live vaccines	YES	YES
	ADEM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		YES	YES
	Encephalitis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Live vaccines	YES	YES
	Myelitis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Live vaccines	YES	YES
	GBS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Some vaccines ⁴	YES	YES
Renal	Acute kidney injury (AKI)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NO ⁵	NO
Skin	Rash	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		YES	NO
	Alopecia	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NO	NO
	Single Organ Cutaneous Vasculitis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	r-VSV platform	YES	YES

¹ Hepatic dysfunction / failure, hemorrhagic disease defined in Brighton CD for Viscerotropic disease.²³⁴

² Hepatic dysfunctions can also be defined using FDA severity scales.

³ Severe CHIKV infection: Brighton [Viscerotropic](#) disease CD²³⁴ recommended; needs some modification to add neurologic organ failure but otherwise the entities seen in severe CHIKV infection are all part of the Viscerotropic disease CD, which requires 2 to 3 of: hepatic injury, AKI, rhabdomyolysis, respiratory failure, thrombocytopenia [$<100,000/uL$], hypotension and coagulopathy. A defined major and minor criterion for each of the organ systems listed is included in the CD.

⁴ Some seasonal influenza vaccines; monovalent H1N1 pandemic vaccine; COVID-19 ChAdOx-1 S vaccine

⁵ For AKI the recommended definition is the consensus KDIGO guidelines (see www.kdigo.org). For children, the modified pRIFLE criteria are recommended as reviewed by Thomas et al. ²³⁶

SPEAC recommends that the listed AESI be adopted by CEPI and the Chikungunya vaccine developers. SPEAC recommends that the developers be prepared to take a uniform approach to the identification, assessment, investigation, analysis and reporting of any AESI should it occur during a clinical trial.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. Subcontractor report of Chikungunya literature review

Prepared for Barbara Law, MD, by Tigest F. Mekonnen, MPH, Rachael M. Porter, MPH, and Erin C. Stone, MPH, Hubert Department of Global Health, Rollins School of Public Health, Laney Graduate School, Emory University.

Methods

This document is a scoping review conducted according to PRISMA Guidelines Extension for scoping reviews¹ to update the Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines Priority list of adverse events of special interest for Chikungunya.

Topic & Question Development

This research question used to guide this review is:

- What is the incidence and clinical presentation for Chikungunya?

Literature Search

One reviewer (E.C.S.) developed a search strategy for MEDLINE from the research question. This strategy was refined using keywords mined from the references of the previous iteration of this document, and then adapted to EMBASE and CINAHL. Searches were performed from the start of each database to February 14, 2024. The results of these searches were uploaded into EndNote 21 (Clarivate Analytics©, Thomson Reuters, New York, NY, USA), de-duplicated, and uploaded to Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation Ltd., Melbourne, VIC, Australia) where a second round of deduplication was conducted. No study protocol was published for this effort.

Study Selection

The titles and abstracts of retrieved references were screened by single review (T.M., R.P., or E.C.S.). Full-text articles were retrieved if they were relevant to the research question and reporting on chikungunya disease course, clinical presentation, complications (including viral-host interactions, immunogenic response, or viral replication response), pathogenesis, or immunologic response.

A study was excluded if:

- No full text was available;
- It was in vitro;
- It was not available in English;
- It did not report primary data;
- Reviewers were not able verify complete methods (e.g., conference abstracts & posters); or
- No exposure or outcome of interest was reported.

The full texts of selected articles and the relevant references of selected systematic reviews and narrative reviews were then screened by single review (T.M., R.P., or E.C.S.). After the full-text screening was complete, the bibliography of the articles selected for inclusion was vetted with subject matter experts.

The results of the study selection process are depicted in Figure 1.

Studies from databases/registers (n = 1325)
 PubMed (n = 1119)
 CINAHL (n = 202)
 Embase (n = 3)

FIGURE 1 Results of the Study Selection Process

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Methodologic data and results of clinically relevant outcomes from the studies meeting inclusion criteria were extracted into standardized evidence tables. Data and analyses were extracted as presented in the studies. For the purposes of this review, statistical significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 1. Primary Search Strategies of Databases: 2/14/2024

Database	Strategy	Run Date	Records
Medline (OVID) 1946-	Alphavirus/ OR Chikungunya Fever/ OR Chikungunya Virus, Human/ OR Chikungunya Infections/ OR CHICKV or (alphavirus or Chikungunya Fever* OR Chikungunya Virus* OR Chikungunya Infection* OR CHICKV) Or "chikungunya fever/complications"[All Fields] OR "chikungunya fever/epidemiology"[All Fields] OR "chikungunya fever/physiopathology"[All Fields] OR "chikungunya fever/immunology"[All Fields] OR ("chikungunya fever"[All Fields] OR ("Chikungunya"[All Fields] AND "Fever"[All Fields]) OR "chikungunya fever"[All Fields]) AND "virology*" [All Fields]) OR "chikungunya fever/etiology"[All Fields] AND ("2019/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "3000"[Date - Publication])	2/14/2024	1119 unique records
Embase (OVID) 1974-	('alphavirus'/exp OR alphavirus OR 'chikungunya'/exp OR chikungunya) AND ('pathophysiology'/exp OR pathophysiology OR 'complications'/exp OR complications OR 'epidemiology'/exp OR epidemiology OR 'immunology'/exp OR immunology OR 'etiology'/exp OR etiology) AND limit AND date AND [2019-2024]/py	2/14/2024	3 unique records
CINAHL (EBSCOHost)	(chikungunya or chikungunya virus or chikungunya fever or chikv) AND (pathophysiology or complications or immunology or epidemiology or clinical course or symptoms or) & DT T1 clv0=201901-202402	2/14/2024	202 unique records

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